

VR TOGETHER EPISODE 1
THE ARMOVA CASE

USER 1 - THE INTERROGATION OF RYAN ZELLER

FADE IN:

INT. INTERROGATION ROOM - LATE NIGHT

The user is sitting on the dark side of an interrogation room, looking at a one-way mirror. Through the mirror they can see the lighted side of the room, a spartan concrete box featuring just a bare table and two simple chairs.

In the user's side of the room, resting on a table in front of the user and a bit to his side, a screen is playing a recording on loop - a CCTV recording showing the entrance to Armova's apartment, with a timestamp: "17.45" We see ZELLER arriving at the door, and going in. The CCTV recording jumps ahead - timestamp "18.19". We see ZELLER going out and walking away. Another cut - "19.25". CHRISTINE arrives, wearing a spaghetti strap dress, her shoulders exposed and pale, no bandage on her arm. The recording jumps ahead - timestamp "22.03". CHRISTINE exits the building hurriedly, clutching her left arm, and runs away. The recording keeps looping.

Enter the SARGE, a middle-aged British cop, a tad jaded, slumped shoulders betraying his tiredness. He closes the door, drops a heavy folder on the table, then approaches the mirror and stares at the user, voice edged with sarcasm.

SARGE

Well, here we are. Back with the cool kids.
Let's make this good, inspector.

He sits on the table and skim-reads through the dossier.

SARGE

What do we have here? Miss Yelena
Armova, age 27...

(holds a picture for a second)

Rather easy on the eyes. Owner of an
hotel empire, found dead in her
Mayfair residence.

(looks up, winks at the mirror)

The tabloids must be all over this, eh?
Guess that explains why the big shots
at Europol got us out of bed in the

dead of night. Alright, let's see it through.

(reads from the dossier)

Next witness, RYAN Zeller, age 34, playboy with a reputation for nastiness, saw Armova before she died.

(raises his voice)

Alright, let's get started!

A few seconds later, ZELLER enters the room, all confidence and swagger. An aging dilettante who hasn't accepted he's not in his twenties any more. His natural insolence and flamboyance are boosted with some substance - he moves erratically and occasionally slurs his words. He stands there for a second, looking around the room.

ZELLER

Whoa. This is the real deal, huh?

SARGE

Mister Zeller, take a seat. Tell us about last night, and especially... mister Zeller?

ZELLER ignores the policeman and heads to the mirror, seemingly fascinated, almost tripping on the chairs.

ZELLER grins and shields his eyes to see through the glass.

ZELLER

Hellooo. Hello? Someone there?
Someone home? You bet...

With a sigh, SARGE approaches, taps ZELLER on the shoulder.

SARGE

Mr. Zeller!!!

ZELLER turns around nonplussed, as if he saw SARGE for the first time - then loses balance.

ZELLER

Not guilty. I didn't kill him, I mean her. Just here for the show.

SARGE

Sir, Have you taken drugs?

ZELLER

(running out of steam)

Drugs? Ha! You call them drugs, I call... it... breakfast.

ZELLER tries to straighten his back and stand but his knees falter. SARGE catches him before he falls, then shoots the user a resigned look through the mirror before helping ZELLER into one of the chairs.

ZELLER
(mumbling)
Oh man, this is a shithole.

SARGE sighs, obviously tired with the whole scene.

SARGE
Not your kind of suite, eh, Zeller?

ZELLER
Well, it's... not the Ritz.

SARGE slams a hand on the table and leans towards him, intimidating. He's had enough.

SARGE
But it's a bloody good warm-up for the jail. You can talk, or you can start getting used to it.

ZELLER claps, laughing, then coughs. He gestures with a trembling hand, pointing at SARGE, the mirror and the door.

ZELLER
Bravo. Hard cop. I've seen this one. You're gonna talk tough to me for a while, and then a nicer guy steps in, maybe a woman, she's all smooth, so I spill. You gonna rough me up too?
(leans forwards, pointing to his own face, hopeful)
Hit me a couple times maybe, for the bragging rights? Nah?
(he sits back, disappointed, gestures around)

I guess all you have is this shit job, right?

SARGE
Alright, here's what I don't get, Zeller. You are filthy rich. You could have avoided this. You waived

your rights because you wanted to talk to us. So talk. Why did you kill her?

ZELLER
Oh, I didn't.

SARGE
You're famous for having a temper.

ZELLER
uhm

SARGE
It doesn't make you look good. You're going to be famous as a murderer. A crime of passion.

ZELLER throws his arms up and shouts festively:

ZELLER
Bravo! Case closed! Well done, Sherlock!

SARGE remains silent, surprised with the confession...

ZELLER
(suddenly serious)
A crime of passion. You got that right. But, alas, I didn't do it. She did.

SARGE
So you're saying it's a suicide?

That sends ZELLER into a fit of laughter.

ZELLER
Not her. HER.

ZELLER points to, in the direction of the other room. SARGE looks towards the user. Right there, the LIGHTS GO OUT for a second, then they come back.

SARGE
(deadpan)
Who were you talking about?

ZELLER
Oh, come on. I know you have that glorified secretary in the can as

well. Always hovering around her
like,

(mimicking CHRISTINE)

"Lena sign this, Lena let me handle
that, Lena you're late, Lena don't do
drugs, Lena don't breathe." Fucking
hell. Lena knew she wasn't working
just for her.

SARGE

Miss Gérard?

ZELLER

Yeah, whatever. The menial.

SARGE

What do you mean, miss Gérard wasn't
working only for Lena?

ZELLER

You think she can afford that with
the pittance Lena paid? Selling her
secrets. I told Lena, she wouldn't
listen. Maybe she told her too,
pillow talk or something.

SARGE

Industrial espionage, eh?

ZELLER

I'm doing your job here, officer.

SARGE

So if miss Gérard was selling
Armova's secrets, who was buying? If
we're talking business competitors,
then right now I'm looking at a
strong suspect. Wasn't she kicking
you out of all major western European
resorts?

For the first time, ZELLER visibly tenses up. He sits a bit
straighter, pauses. Suddenly serious and calculating.

ZELLER

(quietly angry)

That has nothing to do with this.

SARGE

You have motive, opportunity, you're sitting there trying to find a scapegoat. I could sell it.

ZELLER
(interrupting)
You could try.

SARGE
(unfazed)
...or you could tell me what you actually know, if you really believe it was miss Gérard.

ZELLER
(gesturing to the other room)
Well, talk to her! Ask her about her real job, spying on Lena for years...

The outburst makes ZELLER a little dizzy. He blinks, shakes his head to clear it. SARGE tut-tuts.

SARGE
Easy on the booze, Zeller.

ZELLER
I'm fine... a bit under the weather.
Just need to stretch my legs...

ZELLER gets up, carefully, closely watched by the cop.

SARGE
What time did you get to her apartment?

ZELLER walks up to the mirror again. He blinks uneasily.

ZELLER
Eh, six? Maybe five-thirty..
...And then Chris arrived..
...made a fuss..
...We had a drink..
...At eight or so.

SARGE
(nodding at the user)

OK, we'll check.

(back at ZELLER)
We found blood on the crime scene,
Zeller, but it wasn't Lena's. Did
someone get hurt?

ZELLER
Blood? No...

ZELLER gasps for air, eyes wide open.

ZELLER
I didn't... do... do-don't...

SARGE
(impatiently)
I need facts, Zeller! When you left,
was miss Gérard still with miss...

ZELLER retches and drops to the floor, spasming. SARGE jumps
to his feet and tries in vain to wake ZELLER up.

SARGE
What the... Medic! We need a medic!

FADE OUT:

USER 2 - THE INTERROGATION OF CHRISTINE

FADE IN:

INT. INTERROGATION ROOM - NIGHT

The user is sitting on the dark side of an interrogation room, looking at a one-way mirror. Through it they can see the lighted side of the room, a spartan concrete box containing just a table and two chairs.

In the user's side there's an open dossier, resting on the table. It reads: "Forensic analysis of the body: (under way), Preliminary cause of death: widespread trauma stemming from fall from balcony. Forensic analysis of the room has focused on three glasses of whisky, one of them containing chemicals (symptoms: dizziness, euphoria, disorientation, vomit, heart failure if untreated)."

In the lighted side of the room, SARGE is reading a dossier.

SARGE

(he looks up at the user)

Have you read the dossier, inspector?

(he reads)

Yelena Armova, age 27, top businesswoman, darling of the London tabloids, found dead in her Mayfair mansion. No witnesses, no leads.

(winks at the user)

Sounds like we're out on a wing and prayer, eh? So let's close this case soon. I'd rather be having a pint in Margate, instead of a friendly chat with...

(he reads again)

Miss CHRISTINE Gérard, age 30, Armova's assistant. Last person to see her alive.

(yelling)

Send her in, lads!

A few seconds later, CHRISTINE enters the room and stops.

CHRISTINE is a professional-looking woman, composed and conservatively made-up. Her movements and gestures are tightly controlled, as she's trying to rein in her emotions. She's wearing trousers and a short-sleeved shirt, all very office-smart. A big adhesive bandage covers most of her left forearm.

She stands at the threshold for a second, looking at the cop, the table and the mirror.

SARGE
Come in, CHRISTINE. I hope you have some answers for me...

CHRISTINE
(coldly)
I don't think we're on a first-name basis yet. Sir.

SARGE does a mock bow, indicating the chair.

SARGE
Touché, ma'am. If you would be so kind as to take a seat, ma'am.

CHRISTINE sits, reluctantly. SARGE turns to the mirror.

SARGE
Where were you last night? Exact times.

CHRISTINE
I had been reviewing Le... miss Armova's schedule with her, at her apartment.

(Sarge looks at her)

She had to attend a cocktail at the embassy, so we wrapped up and I left.

Must have been nine o'clock.

SARGE
And what time did you arrive?

CHRISTINE
(without hesitation)
Twenty-five past seven.

SARGE turns around to look at her.

SARGE
That's surprisingly precise timekeeping, miss Gérard.

CHRISTINE

I suppose I am a surprisingly precise individual, officer. That's why I am Le... was, miss Armova's assistant.

SARGE

Was she a generous employer?

CHRISTINE

(choosing her words)

She was... correct. Stern, but fair.

SARGE

By which you mean she was stingy as hell and notoriously vicious. You seem pretty well-off, miss Gérard. Your account shows quite a tidy sum, for a secretary.

CHRISTINE

With all due respect, you didn't know miss Armova, officer. I did. She was a great businesswoman, a mentor, and an inspiration. And may I add, my finances are none of your business.

SARGE

(without missing a beat)

Did you hurt yourself?

CHRISTINE

(taken by surprise)

Beg your pardon?

SARGE

Your wrist.

CHRISTINE touches the bandage on her arm, reflexively.

CHRISTINE

Oh, no... well, in a way. I fell down some stairs last week. I hope that's not a crime yet, inspector?

SARGE

Devil's in the details, miss Gérard. So you arrived at miss Armova's

apartment at 7.25 and departed at 9.
We'll check.

(he nods to the user)
Were you two alone during all that
time?

CHRISTINE
(with evident distaste)
No. A... friend of miss Armova was
there as well.

SARGE
Who?

CHRISTINE

RYAN Zeller. They had a... private
conversation, and then he left.

SARGE
What time?

CHRISTINE
I don't recall.

SARGE
That's a surprise. I thought you were
a very exact woman.

CHRISTINE
I was miss Armova's assistant, not
Zeller's. She was supposed to attend
a charity fundraiser in Milan today.
We went over the details and then I
left.

The lights flicker and go out for a second, then they're back.
SARGE walks around the table, her gaze following him.

SARGE
Miss Gérard, would you describe
yourself as a loyal employee?

CHRISTINE
Of course!

SARGE is now standing next to CHRISTINE, so that she needs to
look up to face him. CHRISTINE frowns, uncomfortable.

SARGE

You strike me as an exceptionally devoted employee, you do. Much more than anyone would reasonably expect, considering miss Armova's reputation for cruelty and ruthlessness.

CHRISTINE

(irritably)

And what are you implying, officer?

SARGE

You knew Lena very well, didn't you? Perhaps better than anyone else. How long have you been her assistant?

CHRISTINE

Three years. But she's miss Armova...

SARGE

(implacably)

Three years. Traveling with her, living with her. Must have been quite a bonding experience, Lena and you.

CHRISTINE

(raising her voice, exasperated)

I don't like your tone, officer...

SARGE

(talking over her)

Such an impressive devotion. I can absolutely understand why you didn't want Zeller around her.

CHRISTINE

Zeller wanted her dead...

SARGE

(louder)

And how would you know that? Obviously you had a mission, but you grew too attached to her during those years...

CHRISTINE

(furious)

I won't stand here and...!

SARGE

(drones on, talking over her)
It was more than your job. It was your life. You wanted to keep her to yourself, keep Lena away from men like Zeller...

CHRISTINE gets up, fists clenched.

CHRISTINE

She is Miss Armova to you!

SARGE

...you were jealous. All those years, all your loyalty, and Lena couldn't be faithful to you, she had to get high with Zeller, she never valued what you sacrificed to be with her...

CHRISTINE

(yelling, lost all composure)
She's miss Armova to you! Don't you bloody call her Lena, you pig! You don't know her! Zeller wanted her gone, and I told her! But she didn't listen, so I followed her to the kitchen... confused..., she got angry, Zeller was... she grabbed...

CHRISTINE shuts up abruptly, sits down, trembling, nursing her arm. SARGE follows her movement, squatting to keep eye level.

CHRISTINE

(suddenly calm and cold)
He did it. Zeller. He's your man. I was only trying to protect her from him.

SARGE

And what did you do to protect her?

CHRISTINE

I warned her. I tried to keep him away. She thought he loved her, but it was just business to him...

SARGE

And what was it to you? I think you were working for Zeller, and now that

the going gets tough you're turning on him. Did Zeller tell you to poison her?

CHRISTINE looks at him. Suddenly, she smiles, a mirthless, savage smile. All her shyness is gone. She's in control.

CHRISTINE

What!! Nice try. He's using me to cover his ass. Are you sure it was her that was poisoned?

SARGE

(realising he's made a mistake)
Come on, CHRISTINE

CHRISTINE

I want a lawyer.

CHRISTINE

(interrupting)
I. Want. A. Fucking. Lawyer.

CHRISTINE crosses her arms, eyes defiant. SARGE looks back at her for a couple of seconds, then at the user.

SARGE

I'll be.. Alright, we're done here.

CHRISTINE gets up, and before walking out, she shoots a victorious smile at the user.

FADE OUT: